

NORDIC WALKING: A NOVEL EXERCISE REGIMEN FOR CARDIO-METABOLIC HEALTH. A BRIEF REVIEW

PRIYANKA SHARMA¹, MAYANK AGARWAL², SUNITA TIWARI^{3*}

¹Junior Resident, Department of Physiology, King George's Medical University, Lucknow

²Senior Resident, Department of Physiology, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki

³Professor and Head, Department of Physiology, King George's Medical University, Lucknow.

ABSTRACT

There is an emergent and urgent need for newer modalities of physical activity due to rising prevalence of non-communicable diseases that in part can be attributed to sedentary behaviour. Non-adherence to exercise protocol occurs due to cardio-pulmonary insufficiency, perceived exertion and lack of time. Nordic walk, i.e. walking with the pole is a novel form of physical activity that utilises up to 90% of body muscle mass during walking resulting in higher oxygen and hence calorie consumption without an increased perceived exertion. Thus, the Nordic walk might result in adherence of an individual towards exercise protocol. Moreover, researchers have proved that potential health benefits obtained by the Nordic walk are more than the regular level walking. Nordic walking is a new form of physical activity that originated in late 1990 and apart from providing beneficial health effects it also offers a potential research field for exercise physiologists.

Keywords: Nordic walking, physical activity, adherence.

* Corresponding Author

INTRODUCTION

Disease prevalence due to physical inactivity.

The high physical inactivity levels in India is in part responsible for increasing prevalence of metabolic and cardiovascular diseases. Almost every third person in India is suffering from metabolic syndrome^{1,2} that involve visceral adiposity, endothelial dysfunction, atherogenic dyslipidaemia and insulin resistance³. Metabolic syndrome and cardiovascular disease has escalated to younger age groups^{4,5} and is not limited to high socio-economic status as poorest states of India have a high prevalence of these disorders^{1,4}. Physical inactivity increases the risk of metabolic syndrome by 3.34 times⁶ which is an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Approximately 30-40% risk reduction in cardiovascular disease occurs by being physically active⁷.

Recommendation. As the importance of physical activity became apparent, the health agencies worldwide published many guidelines for the optimal level of physical activity required to maintain and improve the health related

quality of life⁸⁻¹². The American College of Sports and Medicine recommends 150 minutes of moderate intensity aerobic exercise per week or at least 30 minutes/day for five days in a week¹¹. Consensus on physical activity for Asian Indian adults is 60 minutes every day that should include at least 30 minutes of moderate intensity aerobic activity, 15 minutes of work-related activity and 15 minutes of muscle strengthening exercises¹².

Requirement for newer approaches for physical activity. Despite the continuous efforts on the promotion of physical activity by various agencies, the levels of physical inactivity in India is alarming. ICMR-INDIAB (Indian Council of Medical Research - India DIABetes) study in 2014 reported that not only almost half of the adults in India are physically inactive, but also less than 10% are involved in recreational physical activity¹³. Lack of time, perceived exertion, pain and dyspnoea due to cardio-pulmonary insufficiency are frequently quoted causes that prevent an individual from opting a physical activity programme¹⁴. Thus, there is an

emergent and urgent need to involve and evolve newer approaches to physical activity that should be well accepted by the physically inactive individuals.

Few definitions. The terms 'physical activity' and 'exercise' are different; however, often they are used as synonyms. Any bodily movement resulting from contraction of skeletal muscle that leads to the expenditure of energy (calories) is termed as physical activity; while, when the physical activity is planned, structured, and repetitive with an aim to improve or maintain physical fitness, it is termed as exercise¹⁵. The use of term 'aerobic' in exercise means that the energy for muscular contraction is derived entirely from oxidative phosphorylation. However, exclusive aerobic metabolism does not occur as muscle contraction derives energy from both aerobic and anaerobic pathways. The relative contribution of each pathway depends upon the intensity of exercise. Hence, usage of term 'endurance' for long duration exercise with oxidative phosphorylation pathway as a predominant source of energy is more suitable than the term 'aerobic'¹⁶. Henceforth, we will discuss the benefits of the Nordic endurance

pressure, diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, body fat, body mass index, total cholesterol and depression¹⁷. Among different forms of walking the most common ones are uphill, downhill and the Nordic walk. The cardiovascular benefit of uphill and downhill walk was dealt in our earlier work entitled "Acute effect of uphill and downhill treadmill walk on cardiovascular response and perceived exertion in young sedentary individual"¹⁸. The present commentary will focus on the Nordic walking.

NORDIC WALKING. Walking with poles is known as the Nordic walk. The term 'Nordic Walking' or 'Pole Walking' was originated in Finland in 1997. Nordic poles were developed by Finnish ski equipment manufacturer. These poles has a wrist strap attached at its upper end that allow the walkers to perform the full range of motions comfortably¹⁹. Additionally, the poles acts as a support for upper extremity thereby improving balance and stability²⁰. The poles for the Nordic walk are different from those used in trekking. In Nordic walking, the poles are used to push the ground with the upper extremities while moving forward thereby involving greater active muscle mass than the regular walking²⁰.

Fig. 1: Comparison of muscles involved in walking with (Nordic walk) and without poles²⁰.

exercise. This commentary will deal with the few aspects of the Nordic walking that makes it a novel approach to physical activity.

TYPES OF WALKING. Walking is an effective and safe physical activity that has a reasonable adherence rate with the wide-range of health benefits like reduction in resting systolic blood

The length of the Nordic Walking poles needs to be adjusted specifically for an individual so that the elbow remains at 90° when the poles are vertically and in contact with the ground. According to the International Nordic Walking Federation (the official worldwide international federation promoting Nordic walking, <http://inwa-nordicwalking.com>), optimum

length of the Nordic poles can be calculated by the formula: height of an individual in centimetres x 0.68.

Fig. 2: Figure showing additional muscle used in pole walking as per American Nordic walking association²¹.

The use of Nordic poles for walking attenuates the muscle activity of the lower extremities with a possible reduction in the load on hip, knee and foot joints^{20,21}. The involvement of biceps brachii, triceps, deltoid medius and latissimus dorsi is significantly higher in the Nordic walk as compared to walking without poles²⁰ as shown in figure-1. Approximately 90% of body muscles (figure 2) are utilised in Nordic walk²¹ which results in higher oxygen consumption²² and hence calorie expenditure as compared to regular walking. Importantly, the perceived exertion during Nordic walking is similar to regular level walking^{23,24}. Thus, an individual burns an extra amount of calories with no additional exertion while doing the Nordic walk that could result in adherence of an individual towards the exercise programme. An illustrative beginner's guide mentioning the importance and correct usage of Nordic walking has been published online by blogger, editor, writer and outdoor expert Amy Whitley²⁵ that could be referred before getting involved in the Nordic walking.

Nordic walking can be practised to – maintain general health; promote weight loss; enhance muscle endurance and strength. However, the current commentary will only deal briefly with the cardio-metabolic benefits of the Nordic walking.

Cardio-metabolic benefits of the Nordic walking. There are several reviews^{19,26-30} that almost covers the entire range of benefits obtained from the Nordic walking. However, few recent studies have been published since these reviews, and thus we will take into account only those studies which are published in or after 2013. We searched google scholar with keywords 'Nordic', 'walking', 'cardio' to include the studies in this commentary.

Song et al. (2013)³¹ mentions that the Nordic walking improves breathing efficiency as the poles act as a support that stabilises the upper body of an individual. Thus, the Nordic walking could be a useful exercise for old or debilitated individuals with limited exercise capacity. They reported that there was a significant reduction in body mass index of the Nordic walking group as compared to regular walking group and concluded that the Nordic walking might be an effective physical activity for managing obesity. Also, the Nordic walking group was found to be more efficient in decreasing blood lipids than the regular walking group. Moreover, a significant increase in the strength of upper extremity muscles was obtained in the Nordic walking group as compared to the regular walking group, and it was implied that the Nordic walking would be beneficial for enhancing cardiovascular and muscular endurance in elderly. However, small sample size, only elderly female participants and short duration of the study (3 months) were few of the limitations.

Frits et al. (2013)³² reported the effects of Nordic walking on cardiovascular risk factors in overweight individuals with type 2 diabetes. It was found that Nordic walking improved the anthropometric measurements like body weight, body mass index and waist circumference in diabetics with normal glucose tolerance. Furthermore, those who adhered to the exercise protocol showed an improvement in exercise capacity. It was implied that the Nordic walking might be a feasible mode of physical activity for individuals unaccustomed to regular exercise. Moreover, improvement in the body composition and physical fitness was achieved by a relatively short period of moderate

intensity Nordic walking that might encourage the overweight people towards this form of physical activity.

Takeshima et al. (2013)³³ compared Nordic walking with the conventional walking in older adults and concluded that cardio-respiratory fitness was enhanced in both Nordic and conventional walking. However, Nordic walking by additionally increasing upper body muscular strength provided the greatest benefit to overall fitness.

Latosik et al. (2014)³⁴ studied the changes in anthropometric, cardiorespiratory, and functional fitness in hypertensive postmenopausal women after eight weeks of supervised Nordic walking. They reported that the Nordic walking resulted in a statistically significant decrease in systolic blood pressure and increased lower and upper-body strength. Also, there was a decrease in serum levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, and low-density cholesterol after the Nordic walking. It was implied that the Nordic walk training might be beneficial in preventing cardiovascular diseases caused by isolated systolic hypertension.

Piotrowics et al. (2015)³⁵ reported that the home-based telemonitored Nordic walk training has high adherence rate among heart failure patients including those with cardiovascular implantable electronic devices. Nordic walk training was found to be safe as no complications occurred in subjects with the electronic implanted device. Also, Nordic walking proved to be an effective intervention as it improved VO₂ peak, 6-minute walk test distance, duration of workload and health related quality of life. Single centre trial involving only females were the limitations of this study. Similar results were earlier reported by Keast et al. (2013)³⁶ who concluded that the Nordic walking might be a promising alternative to standard cardiac rehabilitation care for improving functional capacity and upper-body strength and for addressing symptoms of depression in patients with moderate to severe heart failure.

The above mentioned beneficial effects of Nordic walking are not comprehensive. Schwanbeck (2014)³⁶ in the book "the ultimate Nordic pole walking book" states that the Nordic walking is all-in-one physical activity with superior health benefits and more effective than the regular walking. The book further mentions the role of Nordic walking in – weight loss; improvement of cardio-power;

prevention of stress, high blood pressure, arthritis and osteoporosis.

CONCLUSION

Nordic walking might prove to be a well-accepted physical activity by all age groups for improving and maintaining cardio-metabolic health. However, we need extensive data for the final concluding remarks that require the exercise physiologists to research on this form of physical activity.

Tisha Palit, a certified Nordic walking trainer from Zurich, Switzerland has established the Nordic Walking Association of India to promote the Nordic walking in India³⁷. Decathlon (a sports goods company) will be launching the specific poles required for the Nordic walk in India around April-May 2018. Nordic walking can be performed on a treadmill with slight modification (increasing the width of treadmill-deck)³⁸.

Nordic walking not only proves to be more beneficial in improving health related quality of life than the regular walking, but also it provides a potential research interest for the exercise physiologists.

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